

Intracellular detection of toxic hypochlorite anion by using a nontoxic rhodamine based sensor

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Manuscript received 21 April 2017, accepted 08 May 2017

Abstract : A simple bio-compatible 2,4-dinitrobenzene and rhodamine coupled probe was designed and synthesized for the detection of highly toxic hypochlorite ion with high selectivity and sensitivity. Practical applicability of the sensor was established through simple and fast naked-eye detection of ClO⁻. Absorption and emission spectra proved the detection ability of the sensor towards ClO⁻. The non toxic behaviour of the sensor in living cells increased its practical applicability and it was effectively applied in intracellular detection of toxic ClO⁻ in living cells.

Keywords : Hypochlorite sensor, Rhodamine hydrazide, naked-eye, intracellular detection, DFT computation.

Introduction

Hypochlorite anion (OCl⁻) is commonly used in daily life as a bleaching agent, disinfectant for drinking water, cooling-water treatment and cyanide treatment in the millimolar to micromolar concentration range¹. However, high level of hypochlorite accumulation causes a lot of human diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, atherosclerosis, lung injury, neuron degeneration, kidney disease, arthritis, and cancer^{2,3}. Therefore, the detection and precise determination of HOCl in the biological systems is the new challenge for the researchers. Among different sensitive and selective methods, fluorescent probes are superior in this respect due to their high sensitivity and fine resolution capability⁴. Moreover, colorimetric chemodosimeters are widely used for the detection of target analytes quantitatively by the naked-eye as well as *in vivo* cell imaging technique⁵. Previously, some useful fluorescent sensors have been reported for the detection of HOCl^{6,7}. But, most of the reported probes for hypochlorite suffer from poor selectivity and sensitivity,

very high response time, and practically unsuitable for biological application⁸. Therefore, the construction of a novel fluorescent chemodosimeters for the easy and accurate detection of hypochlorite in the living cells pays great attention.

Rhodamine based sensors are widely used for biological application due to their well-established photochemical properties such as longer excitation and emission wavelengths, high fluorescence quantum yield etc.⁹. The spirolactam ring closed form of rhodamine moiety is normally non-fluorescent and by the influence of the guests (mostly metal ions) ring-opening state exists to show strong fluorescent character¹⁰. Till now, there are only few reports of using rhodamine moiety as an effective structural scaffold for designing fluorescent chemodosimeters of hypochlorite¹¹.

Herein, a rhodamine based sensor coupled with 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene (**S1**) was designed and synthesised (Scheme 1). The molecule was characterised by NMR and Mass spectroscopy.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of **S1**. *Reagent and condition* : (i) hydrazine hydrate, dry ethanol, reflux, 12 h, (ii) 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene, dry DMF, r.t., 12 h.

Results and discussion

The sensing ability of the sensor (**S1**) was studied with various anions like F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CN^- , AcO^- , HSO_4^- , $H_2PO_4^-$, ClO^- in 40% ethanol in water media. **S1** displayed visual colour change from colourless to pink instantly after the addition of 1.0 equivalent of ClO^- (Fig. 1). In contrast, other anions did not exhibit any colour change with **S1**. UV-Vis absorbance spectrum showed the peaks at 319 nm for only **S1** (1.4×10^{-5}

Fig. 1. Visual colour change of **S1** with different anions.

M) but after gradual addition of ClO^- , a new peak was generated at colour region (559 nm) with increasing peak intensity (Fig. 2). The bathochromic shift (λ_{max} 319 to 559 nm) in UV-Vis electronic spectra strongly supports the interaction of **S1** with ClO^- . This new peak was the indication of spirolactam ring opening form of rhodamine part by the reaction with hypochlorite. No such spectral change was observed in the presence of other anions.

The non-fluorescent solution of **S1** turned to red fluorescent in the presence of ClO^- under long wave-

Fig. 2. UV-Vis absorption spectra of **S1** with 1.0 equivalent ClO^- in 40% ethanol in water.

Fig. 3. Visual fluorescence change of **S1** with different anions.

length UV light (Fig. 3). The solution of **S1** remained unchanged with the other anions. The visual fluorescence change could be easily observed from the emission spectra of **S1** (1.7×10^{-6} M) in 40% ethanol in

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water. The emission peak of **S1** was visualized at 439 nm (λ_{exc} 350 nm) but after addition of ClO^- , a new peak at 584 nm was generated and its intensity increased with the gradual addition of ClO^- up to 1 equivalent (Fig. 4). No such spectral change was observed for other anions. Visually detectable red fluo-

Fig. 4. Fluorescence emission spectra of **S1** with 1.0 equivalent ClO^- in 40% ethanol in water.

rescence of **S1** in the presence of ClO^- only along with the generation of a new emission peak at 584 nm (λ_{exc} 350 nm) with ClO^- also concluded that **S1** is a selective and sensitive fluorosensor of ClO^- .

Probable mechanism for sensing of hypochlorite

Based on the previously reported mechanism¹², we supposed that HClO promoted chlorination reaction took place followed by the opening of the spirolactam ring in **S1**. Here, the hydrazide moiety of **S1** was oxidized by ClO^- to form a diimide intermediate (Scheme 2), which experienced further hydrolysis to produce the strong chromogenic and fluorogenic rhodamine B. The rate of hydrolysis was dependent on solvent because water is highly responsible for the hydrolysis of the diimide intermediate.

Cytotoxicity test

Cytotoxicity test of **S1** was performed to know whether the compound was toxic or not. The toxicity level and practical applicability of the molecule was carried out using MTT assay (Fig. 5). About 91% of these cells remained viable even upon addition of 30

Scheme 2. Reaction of **S1** with ClO^- .

Fig. 5. Checking of cell viability using MTT assay for **S1** and **S1**+NaOCl.

μM concentration of **S1** for 24 h which suggested that the toxicity level of **S1** up to 30 μM was low enough and it could be easily applied for any biological activity including cell imaging study.

Fluorescence cell-imaging study

The long wavelength fluorescence emission property of the **S1** was applied for intracellular hypochlorite detection in living RAW 264.7 cells, which proves the superiority of the sensor. To identify ClO^- in living cell, at first 5 μM of **S1** was incubated into the cells (5% EtOH in H_2O) in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) for half an hour at 37 °C. After half an hour, 5 μM solution of ClO^- was incorporated with the cell and incubated for again half an hour.

Then fluorescence images were captured after processing the cells in the proper way. **S1** containing cells did not show any fluorescent image in red channel of fluorescence microscope but the cells incubated with both **S1** and ClO^- showed a bright red fluorescent in the red channel (Fig. 6). This observation suggested that **S1** could be used as a real time useful molecule for detection of ClO^- in living cells.

Quantum chemical DFT calculation

Quantum chemical DFT calculation was performed using Gaussian 09 program with the help of Gauss-View 5.0 visualization program¹³ to investigate the structural aspects of **S1**. The structures were optimized theoretically using B3LYP/6-311G+(d,p) basis set. The energy optimized structure of **S1** suggested that 2,4-dinitrobenzene moiety was almost parallel to the xanthene part of the rhodamine moiety to maintain the stability of the system (Fig. 7a). The optimization energy value of **S1** (-2095.6415 a.u.) suggested its very high stability. Molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) diagram displayed two different colour regions, where red colour signified the electro negative regions and blue colour was the indication of positive regions (Fig. 7b). Electron rich red regions were mainly distributed around the most electronegative centre of the molecule such as N and O atoms. These regions were responsible for easy deprotonation of the NH group by the influence of ClO^- .

The highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) diagram of **S1** along with their spatial distributions were

Fig. 6. Confocal microscopic images of living cells incubated with 5 mM **S1** with 5 mM ClO^- : (a) bright-field image of the cell, (b) red channel fluorescent image, (c) blue channel images of DAPI stained cells and (d) overlay images of b and c in dark field.

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Fig. 7. (a) Energy optimized structure of S1, (b) MEP diagram of S1.

Fig. 8. Energy level HOMO and LUMO diagrams of S1.

displayed in Fig. 8. From the diagram of S1, it was cleared that the xanthene moiety contained HOMO orbitals whereas 2,4-dinitrobenzene moiety contained LUMO orbitals (Fig. 8). The orbital diagrams suggested the probable energy transfer from HOMO to LUMO i.e. from xanthene part to 2,4-dinitrobenzene part of S1.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, a simple bio-compatible 2,4-dinitrobenzene and rhodamine coupled probe was developed for the detection of highly toxic hypochlorite ion with high selectivity and sensitivity. Practical applicability of the sensor was established through simple and fast naked-eye detection of ClO^- . The detection of

ClO^- was carried out using UV-Vis and fluorescence spectral experiments. The non toxic behaviour of the sensor in living cells increased the practical applicability of S1 and it was effectively applied in intracellular detection of toxic ClO^- in living cells. Quantum chemical DFT calculation displayed the structural aspects of S1. So, this sensor might be useful in future for *in vivo* detection of ClO^- infected cells in the human body.

Experimental

All reagents (AR grade) for synthesis were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich chemicals commercially and used without further purification. Solvents were dried following standard procedures. ^1H NMR spectra

were recorded on a Bruker AV300 instrument using CDCl_3 with TMS as an internal standard. ESI-MS measurements were carried out using a microTOF-Q II 10337 mass spectrometer instrument. UV-Vis spectra and fluorescence spectra were recorded using JASCO UV spectrometer (1.0 cm quartz cell) and Perkin-Elmer LS 55 fluorescence spectrometer, respectively. Fluorescence images of living cells were captured using epifluorescence microscope (Carl Zeiss).

Synthesis of compound 1 :

Rhodamine B (1 g, 2.88 mmol) in dry ethanol and excess of hydrazine (2 ml) was taken in a rb flask and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 h. A light pink precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ethanol for several times to obtain pure compound **1**¹⁴.

Synthesis of S1 :

Compound **1** was taken in dry DMF and 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene was added to it. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. The mixture was then poured into ice water to get precipitate. The precipitate was then filtered and dried followed by purification through column chromatography to obtain pure **S1**.

Characteristic experimental data of S1 :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.87 (1H₁, s), 7.96 (1H₂, d, $J=7.5$ Hz), 7.75 (1H₃, d, $J=6.9$ Hz), 7.63–7.52 (2H₄, m), 7.27 (2H₅, d, $J=7.5$ Hz), 6.59 (2H₆, d, $J=9.3$ Hz), 6.40 (1H₇, s), 6.24–6.22 (4H₈, m), 3.19 (8H₉, s), 1.03 (12H₁₀, s); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 165.6, 154.1, 149.0, 148.5, 148.4, 137.9, 133.7, 130.9, 129.6, 128.8, 128.2, 124.4, 123.5, 122.4, 116.4, 107.9, 97.4, 67.4, 44.1, 12.0; ESI-MS (ES+) (m/z) : 623.41 (M+1).

Procedure for cytotoxicity assay

The cytotoxic effects of the sensor **S1** and **S1**+NaOCl were determined by an MTT assay following the manufacturer's instructions (MTT 2003, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). HCT cells were cultured into 96-well plates (approximately 104 cells per well) for 24 h. On the following day, media were removed and various concentrations of **S1** and **S1**+

NaOCl (10, 25, 30, 50, 75, and 100 μM) made in DMEM were added to the cells and incubated for 24 h. Solvent control samples (cells treated with DMSO in DMEM), no cells and cells in DMEM without any treatment were also included in the study. Following incubation, the growth media were removed, and fresh DMEM containing MTT solution was added. The plate was incubated for 3–4 h at 37 °C. Subsequently, the supernatant was removed, the insoluble colored formazan product was solubilized in DMSO, and its absorbance was measured in a microtiter plate reader (Perkin-Elmer) at 570 nm. The assay was performed in triplicate for each concentration of sensor **S1** and **S1**+NaOCl. The OD value of wells containing only DMEM medium was subtracted from all readings to remove background influence. Data analysis and the calculation of standard deviation were performed with Microsoft Excel 2007 (Microsoft Corporation).

Fluorescence cell-imaging procedure

Frozen human colorectal carcinoma cell line HCT 116 (ATCC : CCL-247) was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (Rockville, MD) and maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Sigma Chemical Co., St. Louis, MO) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Invitrogen), penicillin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and streptomycin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The RAW 264.7 macrophages were obtained from NCCS, Pune, India, and maintained in DMEM containing 10% (v/v) fetal calf serum and antibiotics in a CO₂ incubator. Cells were initially propagated in 25 cm² tissue culture flask in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ and 95% air at 37 °C humidified air until 70–80% confluency.

For fluorescence imaging studies, RAW cells, 7.5×10^3 cells in 150 μL of media were seeded on sterile 12 mm diameter poly-L-lysine-coated coverslip and kept in a sterile 35 mm covered Petri dish and incubated at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator for 24–30 h. Next day cells were washed three times with HEPES (pH 7.4) and fixed using 4% paraformaldehyde in HEPES (pH 7.4) for 10 min at rt washed with HEPES followed by permeabilization using 0.1% saponin for 10 min. Then the cells were incubated with 10 μM of

the sensor (S1) dissolved in 100 μ L of DMEM at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 h in a CO₂ incubator and observed under epifluorescence microscope (Carl Zeiss). The cells were again washed thrice with HEPES (pH 7.4) to remove any excess sensor and incubated in DMEM containing NaOCl (20 μ M) followed by washing with HEPES (pH 7.4) three times to remove excess free NaOCl outside the cells. Again, images were taken using epifluorescence microscope. Before fluorescence imaging, all the solutions were aspirated, and the samples were mounted on slides in a mounting medium and stored in dark before microscopic images were acquired.

Acknowledgement

Dibyendu Sain acknowledges Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), Department of Science & Technology, Government of India for awarding National Post-doctoral fellowship (File No. PDF/2015/000882).

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